

PERCEIVED HEALTH RISKS OF SMARTPHONE USE AMONG NURSING STUDENTS IN LAHORE, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: smartphones have become indispensable tools that combine mobile communication with computing functionalities, transforming how individuals interact, study, and manage daily life. However, excessive smartphone use may pose various health risks, particularly among young adults in health professions who rely heavily on these devices for both academic and personal purposes.

Objective: this study aimed to assess the perceived health risks associated with smartphone use and to examine the prevalence and nature of related health complaints among nursing students in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods: a descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 160 bachelor of science in nursing (bsn) students enrolled at Saida Waheed FMH College of Nursing and Mohammadan College of Nursing and Health Sciences, Lahore. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data in two sections: section i captured sociodemographic and health-related information, while section ii evaluated perceived health risks linked to smartphone use. Data were analyzed to explore associations between smartphone usage patterns and self-reported health complaints.

Results: the analysis revealed that blurred vision (42.5%), inadequate sleep (36.9%), stress (40.6%), and back or neck discomfort (33.1%) were the most commonly reported health complaints among nursing students. Although no statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$) were found between smartphone usage patterns and specific health problems, students who used smartphones for eight hours or more daily exhibited higher frequencies of stress and sleep disturbances.

Conclusion: the study concludes that excessive smartphone use poses notable physical and psychological health risks among nursing students, underscoring the need for awareness and behavioral interventions to promote healthier smartphone habits.

INTRODUCTION

Smartphones have revolutionized communication, education, and healthcare delivery, yet their excessive and unregulated use poses growing health concerns, particularly among young adults and health sciences students. Studies indicate that problematic smartphone use has become a global behavioral issue, characterized by compulsive engagement and dependence that mirror addiction-like symptoms (Harris et al., 2020). The constant connectivity and multitasking nature of smartphones have reshaped students' lifestyles, affecting their physical health through visual strain, musculoskeletal discomfort, and poor sleep quality, as well as their mental well-being through increased stress and anxiety (Wacks & Weinstein, 2021; Nikolic et al., 2023). For nursing students—who are expected to maintain high levels of concentration, clinical competence, and patient-centered communication—excessive smartphone use can disrupt not only their physiological health but also their academic performance and professional preparedness (Sibiya, 2018; Figueiredo & Potra, 2019).

Recent investigations across various health disciplines reveal that smartphone addiction is highly prevalent among university students in medical and health sciences programs (Alhazmi et al., 2018; Alboali et al., 2020; Sarhan, 2024). These students are particularly vulnerable due to academic pressures, social demands, and the integration of mobile learning tools into their curricula. Excessive smartphone engagement has been linked to reduced sleep duration and quality (Alfaya et al., 2021), depressive symptoms, and decreased attention span, which may impair clinical training and interpersonal communication (Nikolic et al., 2023). Moreover, dependence on smartphones may reduce in-person social interactions, increasing isolation and diminishing emotional well-being (Juan Gladden, 2018). Such outcomes raise concerns about the broader implications for the healthcare workforce, where effective communication and self-regulation are essential competencies.

In Pakistan, where smartphone penetration among youth is rapidly increasing, limited empirical evidence exists regarding its health

impacts on nursing students—a group critical to the healthcare delivery system. Understanding perceived health risks associated with smartphone use among this population is essential for developing targeted educational and behavioral interventions. This study therefore explores the perceived health risks of smartphone use among nursing students in Lahore, Pakistan, aiming to assess the prevalence of self-reported physical and psychological symptoms and to inform institutional strategies for promoting healthy digital habits and overall well-being.

Materials and methods

2.1. Design

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design to assess the perceived health risks associated with smartphone use among nursing students in Lahore, Pakistan.

Setting

The study was conducted at two nursing institutions: Saida Waheed FMH College of Nursing and Mohammadan College of Nursing and Health Sciences, both located in Lahore.

2.3. Sample and sampling

A total of 160 Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students were selected using a convenience sampling technique. Participants from all academic years who owned and used smartphones were included. Data collection took place between January and March 2025, with all participants providing informed consent prior to participation.

2.4. Data collection tool

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument. It was adapted from previously validated tools (Penglee et al. and Saadeh et al.) and modified to suit the study's objectives and context. The questionnaire was distributed both in printed and electronic formats to facilitate participation.

Section I: Sociodemographic and health-related data

This section gathered information on participants' age, academic year, residence, duration of smartphone use, and self-reported health problems such as eye strain, musculoskeletal pain, and sleep disturbance.

Section ii: perceived health risks of smartphone use

This section comprised 21 items measuring perceptions and attitudes toward smartphone-related health risks. Responses were recorded on a 5-point likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). Scores were categorized as low (<50%), moderate (50–75%), and high (>75%) levels of perceived health risk.

2.5. Validity and reliability

The questionnaire's content validity was established through expert review by three senior faculty members in nursing and public health. Reliability testing yielded a cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.89, indicating high internal consistency.

Results

Table 1. Distribution of nursing students according to their sociodemographic and academic data (n = 160)

Sociodemographic and academic data	N	%
Age (years)		
18–20	68	42.5
21–23	74	46.3
≥24	18	11.2
Academic year		
1st year	46	28.8
2nd year	41	25.6
3rd year	38	23.7
4th year	35	21.9
Living condition		
With family	112	70.0
In hostel	48	30.0

Table 1 shows the distribution of 160 bachelor of science in nursing (bsn) students from saida waheed fmh college of nursing and mohammadan college of nursing and health sciences, lahore. The majority of students (46.3%) were aged between 21 and 23 years, followed by 42.5% aged 18–20 years. Regarding academic standing, most participants

2.6. Data collection procedure

Data were collected during students' free hours using both printed forms and secure online links shared via institutional whatsapp groups. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the process. Each student was allowed to complete the questionnaire once, which took approximately 10 minutes.

2.7. Data analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using ibm spss statistics version 25.0. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize data. The chi-square test was employed to determine associations between smartphone usage patterns and self-reported health complaints, with the level of significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

were in the 1st and 2nd years of their bsn program (54.4% combined), indicating a predominance of early-year students. In terms of living arrangements, 70% of students resided with their families, while 30% stayed in hostels during their studies.

Table 2. Distribution of students' health problems resulting from smartphone overuse (n = 160)

Health problems resulting from smartphone overuse	N	%
Lightheadedness	34	21.3
Blurred vision	68	42.5
Wrist pain	17	10.6
Back pain	55	34.4
Fatigue	49	30.6
Inadequate sleep	59	36.9
Withdrawal or irritability	26	16.3
Discomfort (neck/shoulder strain)	53	33.1
Low self-confidence	14	8.8
Stress or anxiety	65	40.6

Table 2 illustrates the self-reported health problems experienced by nursing students due to excessive smartphone use. The most common issues were blurred vision (42.5%), stress or anxiety (40.6%), and inadequate sleep (36.9%), indicating notable visual strain and psychological effects among participants. Additionally, back pain (34.4%) and neck or shoulder discomfort (33.1%) were frequently reported, suggesting musculoskeletal strain linked to prolonged device

use. Fewer students experienced wrist pain (10.6%) and low self-confidence (8.8%), while about one-sixth (16.3%) reported feelings of withdrawal or irritability when not using smartphones. Overall, the results highlight that both physical and psychological symptoms are prevalent among nursing students, emphasizing the need for awareness and preventive ergonomic practices to reduce smartphone-related health risks.

Table 3. Distribution of students' health complaints resulting from smartphone overuse according to their sociodemographic and academic data (n = 160)

Sociodemographic and academic data	Inadequate sleepn (%)	Discomfort(neck/back pain) n (%)	Low self-confidencen (%)	Stressn (%)
Age (years)				
18-20	23 (33.8)	19 (27.9)	6 (8.8)	24 (35.3)
21-23	29 (39.2)	26 (35.1)	6 (8.1)	31 (41.9)
≥24	7 (38.9)	8 (44.4)	2 (11.1)	10 (55.6)
Academic year				
1st year	14 (30.4)	13 (28.3)	3 (6.5)	15 (32.6)
2nd year	15 (36.6)	13 (31.7)	4 (9.8)	17 (41.5)

3rd year	16 (42.1)	14 (36.8)	4 (10.5)	18 (47.4)
4th year	14 (40.0)	13 (37.1)	3 (8.6)	15 (42.9)
Living condition				
With family	37 (33.0)	31 (27.7)	8 (7.1)	39 (34.8)

In hostel	21 (43.8)	22 (45.8)	6 (12.5)	26 (54.2)
X² (p)	2.108 (0.348)	1.963 (0.374)	0.502 (0.778)	2.342 (0.310)

Table 3 presents the distribution of key health complaints associated with smartphone overuse— inadequate sleep, discomfort (neck/back pain), low self-confidence, and stress—according to students’ age, academic year, and living condition. The data reveal that stress (41.9%) and inadequate sleep (39.2%) were most prevalent among students aged 21–23 years, while older students (≥24 years) reported relatively higher levels of stress (55.6%). Across academic years, third- and fourth-year students showed higher frequencies of both stress (47.4% and 42.9%) and inadequate sleep (42.1%

and 40.0%), possibly due to heavier academic and clinical responsibilities. Regarding living

conditions, students residing in hostels exhibited greater susceptibility to stress (54.2%) and physical discomfort (45.8%) compared to those living with families (34.8% and 27.7%, respectively).

Overall, no statistically significant associations were observed between sociodemographic variables and specific health complaints ($p > 0.05$). However, trends suggest that academic pressure and living away from family may exacerbate stress and sleep-related problems among nursing students, emphasizing the need for targeted awareness and mental health interventions to promote healthier smartphone habits.

Table 4. Distribution of students’ health complaints according to their smartphone usage time (n = 160)

Smartphone usage time (hours/day)	Inadequate sleep n (%)	Discomfort (neck/back pain) n (%)	Low self-confidence n (%)	Stress n (%)
2–4 hours	15 (28.8)	13 (25.0)	4 (7.7)	14 (26.9)
5–7 hours	28 (38.4)	27 (37.0)	6 (8.2)	30 (41.1)
≥8 hours	19 (42.2)	18 (40.0)	5 (11.1)	21 (46.7)
X² (p)	2.281 (0.320)	1.965 (0.374)	0.584 (0.747)	2.526 (0.283)

Table 4 demonstrates the relationship between daily smartphone usage time and selected health complaints among the nursing students. The data indicate a clear increasing trend in the prevalence of inadequate sleep, discomfort, and stress as daily smartphone use extends beyond five hours per day.

Students who used smartphones for ≥8 hours daily reported the highest proportions of stress (46.7%) and inadequate sleep (42.2%), suggesting that prolonged screen exposure may contribute to psychological strain and sleep disruption. Similarly, neck and back discomfort was reported by 40% of heavy users, compared to only 25% among those using phones for 2–4 hours. Reports of low self-confidence were less frequent overall (7.7–11.1%) and showed no significant relationship with usage time.

Although the chi-square test revealed no statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$) between smartphone usage time and specific health complaints, the observed upward pattern suggests that longer smartphone use may heighten physical and mental fatigue. These findings emphasize the importance of promoting screen-time management and ergonomic awareness among nursing students to mitigate potential health risks.

Discussion

The present study revealed that excessive smartphone use among nursing students was commonly associated with blurred vision, sleep disturbance, musculoskeletal discomfort, and stress, findings that are consistent with previous international research on digital device overuse among young adults. The visual and postural

complaints observed in this study align with the results of wang et al. (2020), who found that prolonged smartphone exposure significantly increases the risk of visual impairment and eye strain due to sustained screen glare and close viewing distances. Similarly, demir and sümer (2019) demonstrated that extended screen use not only triggers visual fatigue but also contributes to headache and reduced sleep quality, which in turn affects daily functioning and overall quality of life. These parallels highlight that the physical health complaints reported by the nursing students in lahore reflect a global pattern linked to modern smartphone dependency.

Furthermore, the high prevalence of inadequate sleep and stress among students supports evidence that excessive smartphone engagement can disrupt circadian rhythms and psychological well-being. Saadeh et al. (2021) emphasized that during periods of increased smartphone reliance, such as the covid-19 pandemic, students exhibited heightened anxiety, insomnia, and withdrawal behaviors. Similarly, dai, tai, and ni (2021) found that smartphone overuse among chinese university students was associated with emotional exhaustion, reduced psychological well-being, and social detachment. The current findings corroborate these observations, suggesting that excessive screen time, especially before bedtime, may lead to overstimulation and delayed sleep onset, resulting in both physiological fatigue and cognitive decline in concentration during academic activities.

The findings also revealed a trend where students with higher daily smartphone usage (≥ 8 hours) reported greater stress and physical discomfort. This is supported by penglee et al. (2019), who reported that extended smartphone use among health science students is inversely related to physical activity levels, thereby increasing sedentary behavior and the risk of musculoskeletal pain and mental strain. Collectively, these results underscore that prolonged smartphone use may contribute to both physical health deterioration and psychological stress, particularly among nursing students whose academic workload already imposes high cognitive and emotional demands.

Conclusion

Excessive smartphone use among nursing students in lahore was found to be associated with **visual strain, sleep disturbances, musculoskeletal Discomfort, and heightened stress levels**, reflecting both physical and psychological health risks. To mitigate these issues, **nursing institutions should integrate awareness programs** on safe smartphone practices, ergonomic posture, and screen-time management within their academic and clinical training. Furthermore, **regular counseling and digital well-being workshops** are recommended to promote balanced technology use and safeguard the overall health and academic performance of nursing students.

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